

Smart Zone-Based Vehicle Speed Control and Drowsiness Detection Using Webcam

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ABSTRACT

This project aims to develop efficient automatic wireless vehicle cruise control at low speeds using RF. The emergence of new technologies and increasing computational power has created real opportunities to implement new robotic controllers and new methods of control theory. This technological advancement and the need for high-performance robots has created faster, more accurate, and smarter robots using new robot controllers, new drivers, and advanced control algorithms. The module in the project is an RF transmitter and receiver module for establishing wireless communication and his DC motor for vehicle motion control. The control unit for the entire system is a microcontroller with an HF receiver module. A DC motor is connected through a motor driver. Each time the vehicle enters a low speed zone, data from the low speed zone RF transmitter is received by the vehicle system. The vehicle's system microcontroller automatically slows down to the speed limit for that zone. The microcontroller checks the data with an embedded program and takes appropriate action on the electric motor. Microcontrollers are programmed using the embedded C language.

Keywords—RF; MICROCONTROLLER; WEBCAM; RASPBERRY PI

I. INTRODUCTION

New high-speed innovation initiation and evolving PC frontiers have meaningfully pioneered new robot control and tested new strategies for control hypotheses. This specialized improvement and elite execution robot requirement has created a faster, more accurate, and more insightful robot using new robot control devices, new drivers, and high-level control calculations. This task presents another practical deployment of the robot control framework. The presented robot control framework can be used for a variety of advanced mechanical applications. Encourages movement along the path. Anything intervening causes the robot to stop and change course. This type of company is highly valuable in ventures that require computerized surveillance. The modules in the enterprise are: HF transmit and receive modules for interpreting long range communications, DC motors for development controllers. The main building blocks of this project are:

1. Battery power
2. RF transmitter and RF receiver.
3. Microcontroller.
4. DC motor drive circuit.
5. RASPBERRY PI
6. Webcam

II. AIM OF THE PROJECT

- To restrict the vehicle speed in sensitive zones using RF technology
- Alerting driver through buzzer by detecting the drowsiness by observing facial expressions using web cam to avoid accidents

III. COMPONENTS AND SOFTWARE

Arduino nano: The Arduino Nano is a little, complete, and breadboard-accommodating board in mild of the ATmega328P (Arduino Nano 3.x). It has quite a lot a comparable usefulness of the Arduino, but in an exchange bundle. It wishes only a DC electricity jack, and works with a Smaller than predicted B USB hyperlink as opposed to a trendy one. The Nano board is the number one in a development of USB arduino sheets, and the reference version for the Arduino stage; for a large rundown of current, beyond or out of date sheets see the Arduino listing of sheets.

Encoder: The purpose of an encoder is to create digital information that can be sent from one device to another. The specific encoder used in this project is the HT12E, an integrated circuit with 8 address lines and 4 data lines. This means it can handle up to 256 different addresses and transfer up to 4 bits of data at a time.

Decoder: In this project, we will use a decoder to extract the required information from the received digital data. An integrated circuit HT12D is used as a decoder, which also has 8 address lines and 4 data lines. This means you can decode up to 256 different addresses and process up to 4 bits of data at the same time. The purpose of the decoder is to get the original information from the encoded signal sent by the encoder.

RF Transmitter and Receiver: A wireless communication system that uses ASK (Amplitude Shift Keying) modulation. The system consists of a hybrid transmitter and receiver module operating at a frequency of 433 MHz. The transmission channel frequency is slightly higher, 434 MHz. The

system has a range of 60 meters. This means that the transmitter can transmit data to the receiver from a distance of up to 60 meters, provided there are no significant obstacles or interference. ASK modulation technique is used to convey digital data by varying the amplitude of the transmitted signal. Overall, this system is suitable for short-range wireless communication applications that require simple and inexpensive hardware.

Arduino IDE: An An integrated development environment (IDE) is a software application that provides a comprehensive development environment for writing, testing, and debugging code. In the context of programming Arduino microcontrollers, an IDE typically includes a text editor for writing code, a message pane for displaying information about the code being executed, a text console for viewing the microcontroller's output, and Contains a toolbar with buttons for common functions. The

Arduino IDE is specifically designed to work with Arduino hardware, providing a streamlined interface for uploading and communicating programs to your microcontroller. This includes features such as the serial monitor that allows developers to interact with the microcontroller and debug their code in real time.

DC Motor with Driver: A motor driver such as the L293D H-bridge IC is used to interface between the microcontroller and the motor. The L293D H-bridge IC is a type of integrated circuit that allows a microcontroller to control the direction and speed of his DC motor by adjusting the voltage and polarity of the motor's power supply. An H-bridge IC consists of a series of transistors that act as switches, allowing current to flow in either direction to the motor. A motor driver such as the

L293D H-bridge IC makes it easy to control the speed and direction of a DC motor with a microcontroller. By sending signals to the motor driver, the microcontroller can control the speed and direction of the motor, thus performing different tasks in different applications

Webcamera: A webcam is a video camera that relays its images step by step to a PC or PC organization. Unlike IP cameras (which use direct Ethernet or Wi-Fi connections), webcams are widely connected via USB, FireWire, or similar connections.

RAPBERRY PI: The Raspberry Pi comes with a System-on-Chip (SoC) called Broadcom BCM2835 containing a 700 MHz processor called ARM1176JZF-S. The firmware includes various "turbo" modes that allow users to overclock the processor up to 1 GHz without voiding the warranty. In addition to the processor, it features a VideoCore IV GPU and was initially released with 256MB of RAM, later upgraded to 512MB. As far as storage is concerned, the Raspberry Pi has no internal hard drive or solid state drive and uses an SD card for booting and long term storage.

IV. INDIVIDUAL MODULES

The transmitter section of the project used a microswitch as the input signal, encoded by an encoder before being sent through the RF transmitter. It transmitted power up to 8 mW at 433.92 MHz, had a range of about 400 feet outdoors and 200 feet indoors, and penetrated most walls. The transmitter accepted both linear and digital inputs, operated from 1.5 to 12 volts DC, and was small enough to be built as a small handheld device. The receiver section received the signals transmitted through the RF receiver and decoded them using decoder logic before sending the data to the microcontroller. The decoded information was sent to DC motors 1 and 2 via DC motor drivers connected to the microcontroller.

A. Transmitter:

Fig 1: Block Diagram of Transmitter

B.Receiver

C. Buzzer Section:

V. MAIN MODULE :

The modules used in the project are: HF transmitter and HF receiver for setting up wireless communication, DC motor to control the movement of the vehicle used.

Components used in this project include RF transmitters and receivers for wireless communication, DC motors to control vehicle motion, and IR sensors for obstacle detection. A microcontroller acts as the control device and is connected to the RF receiver module and DC motor through a motor driver (L293D). The microcontroller is programmed in embedded C language and the embedded program checks the data and takes appropriate action. Every time the vehicle enters the coverage zone, it receives a signal and slows down to cutoff. This is maintained until the vehicle leaves the coverage zone. A 5V DC power supply is required to power the embedded system and can be obtained from a regulated power supply block. A rectifier is used to protect the circuit from reverse battery polarity.

VI. ADVANTAGES

- Vehicle Speed Control with the help of PWM
- Motor Speed Control through RF technique
- Speed controlling near speed breaker
- Supporting drivers with webcam sleep detection mode
- Can be used for U curves prior Intimations

VII. APPLICATIONS

Various industries use RF solutions for a variety of purposes including surveillance, asset tracking, process control, data connectivity and barcode readers. Commercial wireless applications such as door announcers, security and entry systems, gate controls, remote activation, display panels and paging systems also commonly use his RF technology.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

Using GSM and GPS technology, it is possible to obtain real-time information about a vehicle's speed and location and send it to the owner's smartphone or computer at home. Additionally, this information can also be shared with traffic management systems to improve overall traffic management and also obstacle detection can also be added to detect the obstacle ahead and slow down the vehicle before crashing

IX. CONCLUSION

The objective of this project is to prevent accidents in high traffic zones such as schools, hospitals, highways, and U-turns. The system automatically controls the speed of the vehicle without requiring the intervention of the driver. Additionally, it also detects obstacles and stops the vehicle, thereby preventing accidents and eliminating the need for speed controllers such as police officers. The system is equipped with wireless communication, providing a high level of security monitoring and control for busy zones

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